

Mental Health Dialogues Webinar Series

Webinar #2: Digital Applications in Mental Health Support

October 04, 2024.

11:00 AM – 12:30 AM CEST.

Description:

Mental Health Dialogues is a webinar series jointly organised by 7 huge EU Horizon Europe projects on 'Mental Health in Times of Change' including **Reconnected, IMPROVA, SMILE, ADVANCE, ASPbelong, Mentbest, BootStRaP**. For this webinar, we will aim to address the various concerns on integrating digital technologies in promoting and supporting mental health and well-being. We will delve deep into ways in addressing data privacy concerns, motivation and adherence, and human oversight over digital technologies.

Programme:

Introduction (welcome & programme overview) (2')

Opening Speech by **Stéphane Hogan**, Head of Unit, HaDEA.A3 – Health Research (2')

Lightning Talks (3' per project) (21')

All projects: How does your project utilise digital applications for mental health support. Explain the specific technologies and its potential benefits for users.

Moderated Discussion (36')

Addressing data privacy concerns (all projects):

Recent studies reveal growing user scepticism towards digital applications, particularly regarding data privacy. How does your project address data privacy and security for users interacting with your digital tools?

Sustaining user motivation and adherence (Reconnected, Mentbest, BootStRaP, ADVANCE):

Ensuring sustained user engagement is a significant challenge in digital mental health interventions. How does your project design applications that not only motivate initial use but also support long-term adherence, while aligning with both technical requirements and medical protocols?

Human in the loop approach (SMILE, IMPROVA, ASPbelong, ADVANCE):

While digital tools offer valuable possibilities for mental health support, the role of human healthcare professionals remains crucial. How does your project integrate human expertise and oversight alongside digital interventions and ensure that human practitioners are involved when necessary?

Q&A (27')

Final Message (Announcing the Series and the global Registration Link) (2')